

Full Length Article

Radio frequency O₂-plasma treatment of carbon felts: stoichiometric insight into C1s and O1s XPS with correlated Raman and SEM characterization

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ABSTRACT

Surface functionalization of carbon plays a key role in tailoring their interfacial properties for applications in energy storage, energy conversion, structural composites, etc. In this work, radio frequency (RF) O₂-plasma was employed to tailor the surface chemistry of C-felts. The influence of plasma power and treatment duration was studied. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) revealed that oxygen incorporation increases upon plasma treatment with powers up to 100 W, decreasing the C/O ratio significantly, followed by partial recovery at higher powers due to ion-induced etching. High-resolution C1s and O1s spectra were deconvoluted using a stoichiometric correlation strategy to improve peak assignments. Despite the inherent complexity of O1s spectra due to peak overlap and symmetric features, a consistent interpretation was achieved. Hence, by providing a stoichiometry-driven framework we improve the accuracy and consistency of XPS analysis by correlating the deconvolution of high-resolution C1s and O1s spectra. Raman spectroscopy confirmed the progressive increase in structural defects, with higher plasma powers and longer exposures. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed pronounced surface roughening and fiber etching after plasma. Overall, this work provides a deeper insight into surface modification of carbon felt utilizing O₂-plasma and establishes a stoichiometric framework for interpreting complex XPS spectra of oxygen-functionalized carbons.

1. Introduction

Carbon materials represent an important class of advanced materials owing to their exceptional properties such as high electrical conductivity, thermal stability, corrosion resistance, chemical inertness as well as mechanical stability [1]. In order to exploit them in applications like energy storage, energy conversion, water purification, sensors, hydrogen storage and structural composites, their surface chemistry needs to be modified to overcome their low affinity to other materials and make them versatile and compatible to the desired applications [2,3]. Over the past decades, numerous methods including chemical, electrochemical and thermal treatment as well as decoration with nanomaterials have been developed to introduce functional groups onto carbon surfaces [4]. Among these functionalities, oxygen-containing

functional groups are very popular as they can improve interfacial properties such as hydrophilicity and adhesion and can serve as active sites for further chemical reactions [5].

One promising approach for surface modification is via plasma treatment, which offers a clean, efficient, and controllable way for tailoring surface chemistry without affecting the bulk properties of the material [6,7]. Among different types of plasma treatment methods, low-pressure RF plasma has shown great effectiveness in modifying carbon materials. Operating typically at 13.56 MHz and low pressures (0.01–1 Torr), RF plasma produces a non-equilibrium mixture of electrons, ions, radicals, and neutral species that can react with the carbon surface [8].

In such plasmas, molecules of a gas gain kinetic energy from the electric field of the oscillating RF wave. An increase in the average

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velocity of gas molecules drive a range of electron-impact processes, leading to molecule dissociation, excitation, and ionization [9]. For instance, in oxygen plasmas, molecular oxygen can dissociate into highly-reactive monoatomic oxygen at electron energies of ≈ 5.1 eV, while ionization occurs at ≈ 12.1 eV. Although the average generated electron energy typically lies between 2 and 5 eV, the electron energy distribution function (EEDF) contains a high-energy tail that ensures sufficient kinetic energy to generate surface-active sites in many materials [9].

In low-pressure O_2 plasma, surface modification of carbon materials is governed by two competing processes: chemical functionalization by reactive oxygen species and physical/chemical etching driven by energetic ion bombardment. Monoatomic oxygen and oxygen radicals readily attack surface carbon atoms, particularly at π bonds and defect sites, leading to the formation of oxygen-containing functional groups such as hydroxyl ($-OH$), carbonyl ($C=O$), and carboxyl ($-COOH$). Simultaneously, these reactive species promote carbon removal through the formation of volatile CO and CO_2 , resulting in surface erosion [7,10]. The balance between functionalization and etching can be adjusted with specific plasma physical parameters like RF power and exposure time. For example, at moderate power (e.g., 50–100 W), surface activation takes place, introducing polar functional groups and improving wettability; whereas at higher powers (e.g., 150–200 W), increased etching may remove surface atoms, disrupt existing functionalities or even lead materials to crack and collapse (failure) [8,11]. It should be noted that the oxygen functionalities introduced by plasma treatment are metastable and may change over hours to days after processing due to surface relaxation and reactions with atmospheric species [12,13]. This post-plasma aging is an inherent characteristic of plasma-modified carbon materials [14].

Numerous studies have explored the surface chemistry of functionalized carbon materials, although the accurate characterization of the chemical states of surface-bound oxygen is a persisting challenge due to limitations in conventional spectroscopic techniques. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) is often ineffective as carbon strongly absorbs IR radiation, making signals from oxygen-containing groups hardly detectable [15]. Although XPS is widely used, it faces challenges in accurately interpreting data, particularly when analyzing the O1s spectra [16–18]. The overlap of peaks from various oxygen-containing functional groups also complicates the XPS spectral analysis [19]. Nevertheless, the O1s region contains valuable information that, when carefully interpreted, can provide deeper insights than the more commonly analyzed C1s region [20]. Several studies have attempted to deconvolute the O1s peak into 3–6 components based on known binding energies [21,22]. However, a consistent and stoichiometrically accurate assignment remains a challenge due to documented misinterpretations of overlapping signals, differences in chemical environments, and inconsistent fitting practices [23,24]. Recently, several works were addressed to these issues aiming at reducing common mistakes in XPS data interpretation [18,23,25,26]. In this work, we provide a stoichiometry-driven framework to improve the accuracy and consistency of XPS analysis by correlating the deconvolution of high-resolution C1s and O1s spectra. Unlike conventional approaches that fit the C1s and O1s regions separately, this presented method uses stoichiometric relationships between carbon and oxygen species to guide peak fitting and assignment. By integrating quantitative stoichiometric relationships into the deconvolution process, this framework moves XPS interpretation beyond empirical fitting toward a more chemically meaningful interpretation.

In addition to XPS, Raman spectroscopy is a widely used tool to characterize structural order and defects in carbon materials. The ratio between the intensity of disorder-activated D band (≈ 1350 cm^{-1}) and the graphitic G band (≈ 1580 cm^{-1}) gives an indication of defect density [27,28]. As some other smaller peaks might emerge, using the area under each peak instead of the peak intensity can better reflect the total vibrational modes activated by defects. The ratio of D to D' (≈ 1615

cm^{-1}) can differentiate between defect types such as sp^3 functionalization, vacancies, and grain boundaries [29]. These spectral features enable correlation between chemical functionalization and lattice disorder.

In this study, RF O_2 -plasma in low-pressure is investigated as a method for functionalizing the surface of carbon felts. By varying the plasma power and treatment time, the transition from surface functionalization to etching was examined by means of XPS. A rational framework is also provided to systematically correlate high-resolution C1s and O1s spectral interpretations, enhancing the reliability of oxygen functional group identification. Raman spectroscopy and SEM are further employed as complementary analyses aiming at providing deeper insights into the structural and morphological changes of the modified carbons.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Plasma treatment

A Femto-BR-200-PCCE7-c benchtop plasma system (Diener Electronic, Germany) was used for surface modification. Commercial carbon felt (SIGRATHERM® soft felt) was obtained from SGL Carbon. The felts were treated with oxygen plasma at a pressure of 0.40 mbar, with power ranging from 50 to 200 W, for durations between 2.5 and 5 min. Before plasma ignition, the chamber pressure was reduced to below 0.07 mbar. Samples were positioned vertically in the chamber to ensure exposure of both surfaces to the plasma. Mass loss was measured before and after plasma treatment by using a Kern 770 scale with 0.0001 g precision.

2.2. XPS

Surface chemical analysis was performed using a Nexsa G2 X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). X-ray source: monochromatic Al $K\alpha$ radiation. Samples were analyzed under ultra-high vacuum conditions ($\leq 1 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar). To enhance data reliability, measurements represent the average of two randomly selected spots (200 μm in diameter). Survey scans were carried out at a pass energy of 100 eV and an energy resolution of 1.0 eV, whilst high-resolution spectra were recorded at a pass energy of 20 eV and a resolution of 0.1 eV. It is important to note that XPS was performed shortly after the plasma treatment (on the same day) to prevent/minimize aging and preserve the original surface features introduced by the treatment.

2.3. C1s peak fitting procedure

C1s peak fitting was performed using CasaXPS software. To improve the accuracy of C1s peak fitting within this software, we used the following protocol merging empirical experience with literature recommendations:

- A. **Charge Correction:** All spectra were charge-corrected by aligning the binding energy scale to the $C=C/C-C$ peak at 284.8 eV.
- B. **Energy Range Selection:** The energy range of 282–294 eV was selected for fitting the C1s region. This range includes the binding energies for different carbon environments.
- C. **Baseline Correction:** A Shirley background was used to correct the baseline.
- D. **Peak Assignment:** Five peaks were assigned: $C=C/C-C$ (284.8 eV), $C-O$ (≈ 286.1 eV), $C-O$ (≈ 287.2 eV), $C=O$ (≈ 288.0 eV), and $O-C=O$ (≈ 289.2 eV) [30–34]. A shake-up feature was also included for binding energies above 291 eV, correlated with $\pi-\pi^*$ transition effects, although it does not contribute to the chemical composition of the surface.
- E. **Line shape selection:** The $C=C/C-C$ component was fitted using an asymmetric $A(a,b,n)GL(p)$ function.

In $A(a,b,n)GL(p)$: a is the asymmetry factor, controlling the extent of tailing toward higher binding energies; b defines the width of the tailing function, influencing how rapidly the tail decays; n is an integer that determines the sharpness of the asymmetry transition;

p specifies the Gaussian-Lorentzian mixing ratio, where $p = 0$ corresponds to a pure Gaussian and $p = 100$ to a pure Lorentzian. For C=C/C-C components, typical fitting parameters are $a = 0.2$ – 0.3 , $b = 0.2$ – 0.3 , $n = 0$, and $p = 70$ – 80 . In contrast, more symmetric peaks such as those corresponding to oxygen-containing groups (e.g., C-O, C=O) are well-represented using a symmetric $GL(p)$ line shape, with p values typically ranging from 30 to 50 to satisfy the broader nature of these peaks.

- F. **FWHM**: The Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) was constrained according to chemical environment and guided by previous measurements to account for spectrometer-related contributions. Values of 0.7–0.8 eV were used for C=C/C-C components and broader widths of 1.2–1.5 eV for carbon-oxygen-related bonds. These values were determined through iterative peak-fitting optimization and also by acquiring the unconstrained fit parameters for the pristine carbon felts, ensuring physically reasonable line shapes and the good agreement between experimental and fitted spectra.

2.4. O1s peak fitting procedure

Similarly to the procedure described in 2.3, the following protocol was used for fitting the O1s peak, based on accumulated experience and literature:

- A. **Charge Correction**: The O1s spectra were charge-corrected using the corresponding C1s reference peak to ensure consistent alignment of binding energies.
- B. **Energy Range Selection**: The range of 528–538 eV was used to capture baseline curvature and all possible peaks.
- C. **Baseline Correction**: A Shirley background was used.
- D. **Peak Assignment**: Six components were fitted at 530.7 eV (**O1**, C=O in quinones), 532.0 eV (**O2**, C=O in ketones/aldehydes), 532.7 eV (**O3**, C-OH/C-O-C in aromates), 533.5 eV (**O4**, C-O-C in ethers/esters/anhydrides), 534.3 eV (**O5**, C-OH in carboxylic acids), and 535.1 eV (**O6**, adsorbed oxygen) [15,35–38].
- E. **Line shape selection**: All O1s components were fitted using a symmetric $GL(p)$ function with $p = 30$ – 50 .
- F. **FWHM**: The FWHM of these components was constrained to 1.0–1.3 eV.

2.5. Matching O1s to C1s: stoichiometric correlation

The consistency of peak fitting between the O1s and C1s spectra was validated by comparing atomic percentages (at.%). A practical and quantitative approach is to use the atomic percentages (at.%) derived from peak areas. Therefore, the following procedure was applied:

- A. The contribution of oxygen-bonded carbon species in the C1s spectrum was determined by subtracting the C=C/C-C component from the total carbon signal.
- B. The area of each oxygen-containing carbon group was normalized to this O-bonded fraction to calculate their relative distribution.

This procedure is described in detail in the [Supporting Information](#), with a summary provided in [Table S1](#).

2.6. Raman spectroscopy

Raman measurements were performed using a Horiba JY LabRAM HR800 spectrometer. The excitation source was an air-cooled diode-pumped solid-state (DPSS) laser operating at a wavelength of 514 nm with a maximum output power of 25 mW. To prevent material damage

due to excessive energy input, the laser power was reduced to approximately one tenth of its maximum output by using optical filters, resulting in an effective power of about 2.5 mW at the objective. The spectra were acquired with a $100 \times$ LWD objective, yielding a laser spot size of approximately $1 \mu\text{m}$ on the sample surface. The spectrum fit was performed with 6 Lorentzian curves.

Raman spectra were recorded in the range of 900 – 1800 cm^{-1} , where the main graphitic and defect-related modes appear. The spectra were deconvoluted into G, D, D', D3, D4, and, when present, D5 bands.

The estimation of the total disorder S was performed according to Eq. (10):

$$S = \frac{A_{D_{tot}}}{A_G} = \frac{A_D + A_{D3} + A_{D4}}{A_G} \quad (10)$$

2.7. SEM

The morphology of the pristine and plasma treated carbon felts was investigated with a Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM JEOL 7200F, Japan) operating a field emission gun. To preserve the native surface morphology, no conductive coating was applied, as the carbon felts exhibited sufficient electrical conductivity. The parameters for these measurements were chosen as 10 kV, and 10 mm working distance. The samples were placed directly onto a carbon tape on the top of aluminum stubs. Micrographs were acquired using the secondary electrons (SE) detector.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Peak fitting considerations

Charge correction in XPS is crucial for compensating the charge buildup on non-conductive samples, which can cause binding energy shifts and distort the spectrum [39]. This correction ensures accurate chemical state identification, consistent and reproducible measurements, and standardization across studies by aligning the binding energy scale to a known reference point, such as the C=C/C-C peak at 284.8 eV, which corresponds to the binding energy of graphitic carbon – a common component in carbon materials [40]. When only oxygen-containing groups are present on a carbon substrate, five peaks can be assigned, (see [Section 2.3](#)). Assigning peaks in this manner is reliable as with XPS it is challenging to differentiate between various chemical states of C-O and C=O bonds due to their overlapping peaks and close binding energy ranges. Additional peaks may be required if other elements like S, N, Si, F, and Cl are attached to carbon [4].

Accurate fitting also depends strongly on the choice of peak shape. In many carbon materials, especially graphitic or sp^2 -rich systems, the C=C/C-C peak often appears asymmetric rather than in a simple symmetrical shape [31,32]. While some studies try to separate C-C and C=C into different peaks, this can be misleading because their binding energies are very close and often overlap. Recent research shows that the asymmetry in the C=C/C-C peak is not due to separate chemical states, but instead comes from core-hole screening effects [41]. When a photoelectron is ejected, other electrons in the material rearrange to screen the resulting core hole, which causes some photoelectrons to lose energy. This results in a tail on the high binding energy side of the peak. Because of this, it is more appropriate to fit the C=C/C-C signal with an asymmetric peak shape, such as the $A(a,b,n)GL(p)$ function in CasaXPS. This model combines a Gaussian/Lorentzian product function – $GL(p)$ – with an asymmetric modification $A(a,b,n)$ to more accurately represent asymmetric features in the spectra.

O1s spectra are inherently more complex due to the overlapping contributions of multiple oxygen-containing functional groups. However, assigning six peaks can be a good representation of all components. It is recommended to fix or tightly constrain peak positions based on known BEs since it can be much more complicated than C1s peaks due to

symmetry shape of the O1s and highly overlapping of the peaks. Also, it is necessary to maintain consistent FWHM across oxygen-containing peaks. Otherwise, upon optimization of the peak fitting in the software, one peak may grow abnormally and even eliminate the neighbor peaks. Area ratios may be guided by C1s peak areas.

Comparing the relative contributions of oxygen-containing groups in both C1s and O1s regions provides an internal validation of fitting consistency. Stoichiometric correlations between the two spectra can confirm whether the assigned species are chemically reasonable. The closer the normalized group distributions in C1s and O1s, the more reliable the peak fitting. This cross-validation approach strengthens the reliability of XPS-based chemical state analysis, especially when analyzing complex, heterogeneously functionalized carbon materials.

3.2. XPS survey

The XPS results of the pristine sample (Table 1) indicate the presence of 5.9 at.% O, corresponding partly to residual oxygen from the carbon fiber processing and partly to adsorbed oxygen from the air. A trace amount of sulfur was also detected, likely originating from the fiber processing.

Employing O₂ plasma resulted in the functionalization of carbon fiber surfaces. In this contribution, no measurements took place for powers below 50 W. As indicated by the XPS survey spectra for the 2.5 min plasma treatment, the oxygen content increased from approximately 18 at.% to 25 at.% as the plasma power increased from 50 to 100 W (see Fig. 1). In the corresponding C1s high-resolution spectra (Fig. 2a), a noticeable decrease in the C=C/C-C peak intensity was observed, accompanied by the growth of peaks at higher binding energies, indicating oxygen bound to carbon in various chemical states, such as C-O, C=O, and O-C=O. Within this moderate power range, oxygen-containing functional groups formed extensively. Conversely, when the plasma power was increased further from 150 to 200 W, the superficial oxygen content decreased to around 13–14 at.%. This reduction suggests that ion bombardment at elevated power levels leads to partial etching of the previously grafted oxygen functionalities, particularly the less stable multi-bonded groups [42,43]. This trend is more clearly observed by considering the carbon-to-oxygen elemental content ratio (C/O) (Fig. 1), which decreases as the plasma power increases up to 100 W, indicating progressive oxidation, and then increases beyond 100 W due to the onset of surface etching and loss of

Table 1

Surface chemistry of pristine and O₂ plasma-treated carbon felts analyzed by XPS.

Plasma power (W)	Duration (min)	C (at. %)	O (at. %)	S (at. %)	C/O	Mass loss (%)
0 (pristine)	0	93.2 ± 0.1	5.9 ± 0.4	1.2 ± 0.3	15.9	
50	2.5	82.4 ± 0.6	17.6 ± 0.6	–	4.7	2.1 ± 0.1
		78.0 ± 1.4	22.0 ± 1.4	–	3.5	3.1 ± 0.1
		75.4 ± 0.3	24.6 ± 0.3	–	3.1	4.1 ± 0.4
150	5	86.2 ± 0.1	13.8 ± 0.1	–	6.2	5.8 ± 0.8
		87.1 ± 0.6	12.9 ± 0.6	–	6.7	6.9 ± 0.5
50	5	73.6 ± 0.8	26.4 ± 0.8	–	2.8	5.1 ± 0.2
		69.8 ± 2.1	30.2 ± 2.1	–	2.3	7.1 ± 0.8
		68.6 ± 2.5	31.4 ± 2.5	–	2.2	8.1 ± 0.2
150	5	85.9 ± 0.5	14.1 ± 0.5	–	6.1	10.4 ± 0.1
		86.6 ± 0.5	13.4 ± 0.5	–	6.5	12.4 ± 0.8

Fig. 1. Carbon-to-oxygen (C/O) atomic ratio derived from XPS survey spectra (left Y-axis) and relative mass loss of O₂ plasma-treated carbon felts (right Y-axis) as a function of plasma powers (0–200 W) for treatment durations of 2.5 and 5 min.

oxygen groups. In addition, mass loss of the samples due to plasma treatment increased as a function of plasma power (Fig. 1).

A similar trend for the oxygen content was observed for the 5 min plasma treatments. As shown in Table 1, when the plasma power was in the range from 50 to 100 W, the oxygen content increased both faster and higher than for the 2.5 min plasma treatment. This accelerated raise is probably attributed to the extended exposure time, enabling more oxygen-containing groups to attach to the carbon fiber surface. In contrast, for plasma powers from 150 to 200 W, the oxygen content again declined to 13–14 at.%, and the elemental C/O ratio followed the same inverted trend, initially decreasing with powers up to 100 W, then increasing at higher powers. However, the mass loss in this case was approximately twice as high as with the 2.5-minute plasma treatment, indicating greater material removal with longer exposure times.

These results suggest that surface functionalization rapidly occurs upon plasma exposure at powers of 50–100 W, reaching oxygen contents of up to ≈ 30 at.% within a few minutes. This appears to represent a saturation point, beyond which further increase in treatment time does not significantly enhance oxygen incorporation. However, when the plasma power exceeds 150 W, the process transitions from pure functionalization to a combination of functionalization and etching.

3.3. C1s region

The high-resolution C1s spectra provide detailed insight into the evolution of surface functional groups in dependence of the plasma treatment parameters. At plasma power between 50 and 100 W, the carbon tail extends to binding energies beyond 290 eV, with a pronounced peak around 287 eV, corresponding to C–O bonds. Additional contributions from C–OH, C=O, and O–C=O groups are also evident, indicating the formation of diverse oxygen-containing functionalities.

For the 2.5 min treatments within this power range, the content of C–OH remains relatively constant (≈ 6–11 at.%), while the concentrations of C–O, C=O, and O–C=O groups increase noticeably (Fig. 2 a and b). However, at higher power range (≥ 150 W), the chemical profile shifts significantly: the C–OH fraction increases to ≈ 17 at.%, whereas the contributions from C=O and O–C=O vary slightly, and the C–O component drops sharply from > 22 at.% to around 6 at.%.

In the 5 min treatments (Fig. 2 c and d), the formation of oxygen functionalities in the low-power range is faster than in the 2.5 min ones, as the oxygen content amounted to more than 26 at.% when plasma power was 50 W. In comparison to 2.5 min treatment, the contribution

Fig. 2. Deconvoluted high-resolution C1s spectra of pristine and O₂ plasma-treated carbon felts at plasma powers of 50–200 W for treatment durations of 2.5 min (a) and 5 min (c). (b, d) Corresponding relative contributions of functional groups derived from the C1s spectra under the same conditions.

of O–C=O is roughly two times higher, implying that longer exposure times favor the formation of more complex oxygen-containing groups that require higher activation energies.

Within the high-power range (150–200 W), the behavior is roughly consistent with that observed in the 2.5 min treatments: the surface chemistry is dominated by etching. These results suggest that when the plasma power exceeds a critical threshold (100 W), the chemical state of the surface becomes independent of treatment time, as etching dominates and limits the accumulation of oxygen-containing groups.

3.4. O1s region

Detailed interpretation of O1s high-resolution spectra of O functionalized carbon is valuable as it can provide complementary information about the surface chemistry along with C1s. However, the O1s region is often considered more challenging to analyze because of its typically symmetric shape, which results from multiple strongly overlapping peaks. In the literature, researchers typically assign three to six peaks to O1s of functionalized carbon, as oxygen can be bound to carbon

Fig. 3. Deconvoluted high-resolution O1s spectra of O₂ plasma-treated carbon felts at plasma powers of 50–200 W for treatment durations of 2.5 min (a) and 5 min (c). (b, d) Corresponding relative contributions of functional groups derived from the O1s spectra.

in a variety of chemical states [22,38]. However, in many studies, there is a poor agreement between the areas of correlated components in O1s and C1s.

In 2.5 min treated samples (Fig. 3a), at first glance, the overall shape of the O1s does not significantly change up to power of 100 W, and it seems only the peak intensity is growing. Beyond this point, in the etching dominant range of power, the apex of the peak diminishes while the tail grows, particularly at higher binding energies. Deconvolution reveals that [O1] and [O2], which correspond to C=O groups, decrease slightly when plasma power was ≤ 100 W, but then increase gently at powers ≥ 150 W (Fig. 3b). [O3], which is assigned to C–OH/C–O–C in aromates has the highest contribution among all components at powers ≤ 100 W (ca. 40 at.% at 50 W), drops to around 26 at.% as the plasma power increases to 200 W. [O4] corresponding to C–O–C in ethers/esters/anhydrides shows a steady increment at powers ≤ 100 W, rising from 23 at.% to 30 at.%, followed by a slight decline to 27 at.% at higher powers. [O5] assigning to C–OH in carboxylic acids increases slowly but consistently from 9 at.% to 14 at.% with increasing plasma powers up to 100 W. This trend is interrupted by a minor drop at 150 W and finally peaks at 200 W with 14 at.%. [O6], which corresponds to adsorbed oxygen, initially amounts to below 3 at.% but rises to more than 7 at.% when the plasma power exceeds 150 W. Similar behavior was observed for the 5 min treated samples (Fig. 3 c and d).

To validate the peak fitting, the procedure described in Section 1.4 was applied and demonstrated for the sample treated for 2.5 min at 50 W (see Supporting Information). For the remaining samples, calculations were performed and the results are summarized in Tables S2 and S3. The stoichiometric comparison of the normalized C1s and O1s components reveals excellent agreement, as the ratios $(a1 + a2)/(O3 + O4)$, $(a3 + a4)/(O1 + O2)$, and $a5/O5$ range between 0.9 and 1.1, corresponding to inconsistencies below 10%. This confirms that the peak-fitting strategy applied here is chemically consistent and provides reliable assignments of oxygen functionalities. However, several limitations should be considered. First of all, the background correction should be precise, as it can contribute significantly to the correlated O1s and C1s peak areas. For the graphitic contributions also the satellite feature has to be included to the peak interpretation. Owing to differences in inelastic mean free paths, C1s and O1s photoelectrons exhibit slightly different surface sensitivities and may therefore probe non-identical near-surface volumes, particularly for plasma-treated carbons with increased roughness or heterogeneity. As the present approach is based on relative peak contributions rather than absolute intensities, the impact of these sensitivity differences is mitigated. In addition, the O1s region may include contributions from physisorbed or weakly bound oxygen species, which can increase the O1s intensity without a direct stoichiometric counterpart in the C1s spectrum. In the present study, such contributions were minimized by performing XPS measurements shortly after plasma treatment under high-vacuum conditions, resulting in only minor O1s components attributable to loosely adsorbed oxygen. The remaining small differences can be attributed to uncertainties inherent to the peak-fitting process (e.g., line-shape constraints). These effects are commonly reported in XPS studies of oxygenated carbons [18,23].

3.5. Raman spectroscopy

To accurately study the type and extent of disorders, the Raman spectra were deconvoluted into individual contributions from the G band (ordered sp^2 domains) and several defect-activated bands, namely D, D', D3, and D4, following established decomposition protocols [44,45]. In some cases, a weak D5 band (≈ 1700 cm^{-1}) was also detected, commonly attributed to carbonyl (C=O) vibrations embedded in a disrupted lattice [46]. The ratio of defect-activated band area to that of the G band reflects the overall disorder level. The parameter S in 2.6. can be considered an area-based analogue of the classic ratio of D band intensity to G band intensity $I(D)/I(G)$, which is widely used along the Ferrari–Robertson amorphization trajectory [47]. Each of the defect-

related components provides complementary insight: The D3 band (≈ 1500 cm^{-1}) is characteristic of amorphous carbon or mixed sp^2 - sp^3 bonding, while the D4 band (≈ 1200 cm^{-1}) is attributed to disordered sp^2 - sp^3 configurations or polyene-like fragments [48]. In contrast, the D' band (≈ 1615 cm^{-1}), originating from intra-valley scattering, is particularly sensitive to vacancy-like defects generated under high-energy ion bombardment and will not be considered in S [29].

Representative Raman spectra of pristine and plasma-treated felts are shown in Fig. 4. Consistent with the spectral deconvolution described in 2.6., the fitted components reveal the main graphitic G band along with several disorder-activated contributions. As summarized in Table 2, the pristine carbon felt exhibits a S ratio of 2.5. This value increased slightly to 2.7 after plasma exposure at 50 W for 2.5 min, and to 2.9 after the same duration at 200 W, indicating a gradual increase in defect density with increasing plasma power. Extending the treatment to 5 min further increases this ratio between 3.0 and 3.3, confirming that prolonged plasma exposure enhances structural disorder. The progressive growth of the D3 and D4 components reflects an ongoing amorphization process and the development of short-range disorder, whereas the increasing contribution of the D' band signals the emergence of vacancy-type defects under ion bombardment [29,48].

These Raman findings are consistent with XPS results, which revealed a progressive increase in oxygen content up to ≈ 30 at.% at moderate plasma power and duration. The appearance of oxygenated functional groups in the C1s spectra (C–O, C=O, and O–C=O) indicates that plasma-induced vacancies are decorated with covalently attached oxygen functionalities. However, Raman still detects the underlying lattice disruption because the sp^2 network remains structurally distorted even after oxygen incorporation. In other words, oxygen groups can passivate the defect sites chemically, but they do not fully restore the original hexagonal lattice, leaving a residual signature of vacancy-like disorder.

At higher plasma powers (≥ 150 W), XPS showed a marked decrease in oxygen content (≈ 13 at.%), which is attributed to etching of previously grafted oxygen groups under intense ion bombardment. Yet, Raman revealed a continued rise in S and stronger D' contributions, reflecting the accumulation of vacancies and lattice damage even as some oxygen groups are removed. The apparent difference demonstrates the complementary nature of the two techniques that XPS investigates the evolving surface chemistry, while Raman reveals the persistent structural disorder of the carbon backbone. The results confirm that oxygen plasma simultaneously introduces lattice disorders and stabilizes them through oxygen functionalization at moderate power, whereas the process is dominated by etching and introducing more defects at higher powers.

3.6. SEM

The surface morphology of the fibers before and after plasma treatment was investigated by means of SEM and is shown in Fig. 5. The pristine felt exhibited a smooth surface without noticeable features. After 2.5 min of plasma exposure, the effect of increasing plasma power became evident. At 50 W, the fibers displayed blister-like features and initial surface roughening. Increasing the power up to 100 W produced more pronounced erosion and roughness, which is consistent with other published reports [42]. Interestingly, at 150 W the surface appeared relatively smooth in certain regions, likely due to localized removal of outer layers along with some large grooves indicating a higher extent of erosion. At 200 W, severe surface degradation occurred, with fibrillation and extensive surface damage becoming dominant. For the 5 min treatments, the overall trends were similar but more pronounced, demonstrating the combined influence of treatment time and plasma power. At 50 W, fibers exhibited moderate surface roughening, while at 75 W distinct striations were observed. Increasing the power to ≥ 100 W led to progressive etching and groove development. SEM micrographs with lower magnification from the same spots are shown in Fig. S1.

Fig. 4. Deconvoluted Raman spectra of (a) pristine and O_2 plasma-treated carbon felts subjected to plasma powers of 50–200 W for treatment durations of (b–f) 2.5 min and (g–k) 5 min.

These morphological changes observed via SEM directly align with the findings from XPS and Raman spectroscopy, confirming the chemical and structural modifications induced by the plasma treatment.

3.7. Correlation of XPS, Raman and SEM findings

The combination of XPS, Raman and SEM results provide a clear picture of how RF O_2 -plasma in low-pressure changes the surface chemistry and morphology of carbon felts. XPS shows that oxygen-containing groups (C–OH, C–O, C=O, O–C=O) first increase at low to moderate plasma powers but then level off or even decrease under stronger conditions. Raman at the same time shows stronger signals from defects (higher D_{tot}/G ratios and more D' contribution), which point to growing vacancy-type defect and loss of ordered graphitic structure. SEM micrographs confirm these changes by showing the surface evolving from slight roughness and small pits at gentle treatments to deep grooves at higher power or longer treatment.

These findings are in good agreement with earlier studies: Research on graphite felt and glassy carbon has shown that moderate plasma treatments increase oxygen groups and surface area, whereas stronger treatments cause etching, higher disorder and surface damage [42,43,49,50]. The Raman changes observed follow the model of Ferrari and Robertson, which explains how carbon disorder evolves, and are consistent with the defect-type analysis of Eckmann et al., where the D/D' ratio is used to identify vacancy-like defects [29,47]. Literature on XPS further emphasizes that peak fitting in the C1s and O1s regions should be constrained by stoichiometry to avoid misinterpretation [16,18,39]. The progressive roughening, pit formation and fiber fibrillation revealed by SEM closely resemble the morphological transitions reported by Tang et al. [42] and Domingo-García et al. [43], where micropore development and eventual surface damage occurred as treatment harshness increased.

4. Conclusion

This study investigates the effects of RF O_2 -plasma under low pressure on carbon materials, demonstrating its efficacy as a tunable method for surface functionalization with oxygen-rich groups while highlighting the delicate balance between oxidation and etching. Surface chemistry was tuned in a controlled manner by varying plasma power and exposure time, with highest level of functionalization observed at moderate powers (100 W), beyond which ion bombardment induced material degradation and reduced oxygen incorporation. The innovative stoichiometric correlation between C1s and O1s XPS spectra provided a robust framework for peak deconvolution, enabling precise identification of functional groups. Complementary Raman spectroscopy revealed increasing structural disorder, particularly by increased vacancy defects and amorphization upon increasing plasma power and duration of the treatment. SEM imaging illustrated morphological evolution from localized defects at low powers to extensive striations and etching at higher intensities. The textural changes intensified with prolonged exposure, which was consistent with the findings from XPS and Raman spectroscopy. These integrated analyses offer a comprehensive understanding of plasma-induced modifications, advancing methodologies for XPS interpretation in oxygen functionalized carbon materials. The findings establish a practical guide for tailoring plasma parameters to optimize surface properties, paving the way for enhanced performance in applications such as energy storage devices, catalytic supports, and environmental technologies.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ahmad Alem: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Yining Huang:** Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Nicole Wechner:** Writing – review & editing,

Table 2Normalized Raman band area fractions and overall disorder parameter (S) of pristine and O₂ plasma-treated carbon felts.

Plasma power (W)	Duration (min)	D (1349 cm ⁻¹)	G (1591 cm ⁻¹)	D4 (1146 cm ⁻¹)	D3 (1510 cm ⁻¹)	D' (1627 cm ⁻¹)	S
0 (pristine)	0	62.1	29.0	3.7	3.6	1.5	2.5
50	2.5	62.1	28.0	3.7	3.5	2.7	2.7
75		62.5	26.4	3.7	4.7	2.8	2.9
100		63.0	24.9	3.4	5.1	3.5	2.9
150		62.4	24.8	4.3	4.6	3.9	2.9
200		61.9	24.7	4.7	4.7	3.9	2.9
50	5	62.4	24.6	4.1	4.4	4.4	3.0
75		62.0	23.9	4.6	5.7	3.8	3.1
100		62.0	23.4	5.1	5.8	3.7	3.1
150		61.2	23.4	5.5	6.4	3.5	3.2
200		60.8	23.0	6.3	6.2	3.6	3.3

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs of (a) pristine and (b–k) O₂ plasma-treated carbon felts subjected to plasma powers of 50–200 W for treatment durations of (b–f) 2.5 min and (g–k) 5 min.Validation, Investigation. **Michael Feuchter:** Writing – review &

editing, Validation. **Matheus A. Tunes:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation. **Christoph Rameshan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Stefan Spirk:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Christine Bandl:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Stefan Spirk reports financial support was provided by European Innovation Council. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2026.166208>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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